

The long-term effect of foot insoles on kinetic gait parameters in female children with flexible flat foot

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Abstract— Children flatfoot is a frequent deformity in which there is a reduction in the medial longitudinal arch. Previous studies afford useful information about the prompt effects of foot insoles (FI). It is not clear if these effects long-lasting or might change over a longer period. The aim of this study was to investigate if wearing FI for a long time might change gait variables in children with flexible flat feet (FFF). Thirty Female children (9-13 years) with asymptomatic bilateral FFF were selected according to their arch index. Vicon 3D Gait analysis was used to calculate the kinetic variables (ankle, knee, and hip peak moments) during the gait cycle before and after 6 and 12- months period of wearing the FI. Significant decrease was achieved in terms of foot eversion and forefoot, knee and hip abduction and hip flexion peak moments after 6-months of wearing the FI. After 12-months, the previous parameters continued to decrease, in addition to significant increases were found in ankle dorsiflexion and forefoot adduction peak moments, and significant decreases were obtained in foot plantar-flexion and inversion, knee flexion, extension, and internal rotation and hip extension and internal rotation moments. It could be concluded that FI is feasible and effective in improving the lower limb kinetic parameters by achieving permanent changes in the young females with FFF when applied for successive 12 months.

Keywords— Flexible flat foot, gait biomechanics, kinetic parameters, foot orthoses.

1. Introduction

The greater percentage of youth attend orthopedic clinics with flatfeet. In spite of decreasing the percentage with the passing of age, still, about 15% of them sustain the flat arch [1]. The Flatfoot is expressed as lowering of the medial longitudinal arch (MLA) of the foot than the normal values. It is divided into two types (flexible and rigid) building upon the arch shape in the non-weight bearing position [2].

A flexible flat foot (FFF) is characterized by the presence of the MLA in the non-weight bearing position (sitting), while the arch disappears in the weight-bearing position [3]. It may be asymptomatic or symptomatic [4], Unilateral and/or bilateral [5-7].

Lowering of the MLA often associated with greater pronation of the subtalar joint which may result in other lower limb kinetic chain musculoskeletal problems [1]. During normal gait cycle, the subtalar joint pronates during the beginning of the stance phase [8-9]. This makes the transverse tarsal joints more mobile and permits the foot to accommodate irregular surfaces. After this pronation, supination of the subtalar joint occurs, until the mid-stance phase. During the toe-off phase, the foot becomes a rigid lever by more supination movement [10-11].

In subjects with FFF, after loading response the subtalar joint is still pronated. The transverse tarsal joint is unlocked and the forefoot still mobile in reverse of a fixed lever for next step and re-supination is delayed [10]. So, the plantar ligaments must endure the excess and sustained tensile stress resulted from the unexpected pronation range and the delay of re-supination [5]. The extra subtalar joint pronation results in a prolonged medial tibial rotation. With time, the abnormal mechanics arising from the collapsed MLA is transmitted to adjacent regions like hips, knees, and lumbar spine [4], and therefore flatfoot is considered as a predisposing factor in many orthopedic conditions, such as plantar fasciitis, achilles tendonitis and patellofemoral pain syndrome [12-16].

It was established that flat foot is combined with increased tibial rotation which in turn leads to altered shear stress on the articular contact area of the knee joint [9]. In addition, flat foot not only causes internal tibial rotation but also increase the hip internal rotation range. These changes result in altered hip abductor moment arm, increased knee joint Q angle and overstress the lateral patellar posterior surface. At the spinal level, previous work showed that flat foot can affect the degree of lumbar acceleration during running, pelvic alignment, and erector spinae myoelectric activity [17]. Moreover, it was found that abnormal biomechanical changes in FFF patients create a greater peak plantar flexor ankle moment and invertor moment during the stance phase of walking [18].

There is a considerable conflict considering the treatment of this problem if it must be managed or not. Previous investigators have favored that the FFF will be self-repaired in young children, demanding no treatment except for subjects with hereditary or neurological complications [5]. on the other hand, Lin et al. [19] concluded that the kinematic and the kinetic changes during gait in children with FFF may lead to lower limb pathology later in life. This illustrates the necessity of the use of insoles or corrective shoes for the management of those children.

Foot orthoses (FO) are commonly prescribed methods for FFF [12-14, 20-21]. These include various types of medical shoes, heel modifications, arch orthotics, and shoe insoles [20-22].

Foot insoles (FI) were found to improve the arch alignment, increase the stance time, and decrease the foot pronation angle and consequently the amount of medial rotation of the tibia [5,14,16,21-24]. Furthermore, it was found that the use of orthoses can decrease the peak ankle evtor moment, knee and hip abductor moments and hip flexor moment in the dominant lower limb [18].

Previous work revealed useful data on the immediate effects of the orthotic insoles on patients with FFF. But until now, only one published research which aimed to evaluate the effect of 4- months arch support FO treatment versus a sham condition on lower limb gait variables during walking in boy children with FFF [18].

Some studies reported differences in the gait characteristics between females and males. They precisely showed that the females have more pelvis and trunk rotation, hip abduction/adduction, hip rotation, knee abduction as well as increased ankle flexion/extension in comparison to males [25-27].

Regarding earlier studies and due to the noted sex differences in biomechanical gait parameters, young females were selected to participate in this study. Thus, the aim of this study was to investigate if using orthoses for a longer time (12 months) might change the three- dimensional kinetic gait parameters in female children with FFF.

2. Methods

2.1 Subjects

Thirty female children with normal body mass index and aged 9 to 15 years were selected to participate in this study. This age range was selected to ascertain that the developmental flat feet were excluded [17]. All children have bilateral asymptomatic FFF and were chosen after detecting their foot abnormality from their footprints. They all having an arch index (AI) ≥ 0.260 . The participants were recruited from Prince Sattam Bin Abdulaziz University hospital. They were excluded from the study if they had; any previous history of bone fractures, surgery, orthopedic disease, or neuromuscular problems; had used any arch support insoles before; had any fixed foot deformity; had Leg length asymmetry greater than 5 mm; or had any lower limb trauma or inflammatory joint disease in the past 6 months. The study was applied after signing a consent form by the participant's parents who was informed by the consent before. Ethical approval was obtained from Prince Sattam Bin Abdul-Aziz University Ethics Committee before the study initiated.

Data collection

- Each subject goes through a lower limb musculoskeletal examination. Ankle and subtalar joint range of motion was done to be assured that they all had flexible flat feet bilaterally [5].
- The AI of each participant was computed to detect the degree of flatfoot. It was described as the proportion of the contact area in various parts of the toeless footprint. AI is determined as the ratio of the middle third to the total area of the footprint [5,28]. Subjects with arch indices ≥ 0.260 were considered to have flatfoot; subjects with arch indices between 0.210 - 0.260 were considered normal; and subjects with arch indices ≤ 0.210 were considered to have a high arch [29]. This measurement is considered reliable by many researchers and is supported as an evaluative method for flatfoot [4,10,30].
- Then the subjects were asked to wear a pair of standard laced leather shoes with firm heel counter and flexible sole containing the semi-rigid FI for at least six hours daily during 12- months treatment period.
- The participants or their parents would have a telephone call every week to assure that they wear shoes all over the predetermined hours and follow all the study instruction.
- The insoles were prefabricated and formed from ethylene vinyl acetate (EVA) plastic. They covered about 2/3 of the foot length, from the heel to the base of the first metatarsal head. Its thickness was nearly 2 mm beneath the heel and ranged from 10 to 15 mm in the arch center which would depend on the orthotic length [31]. The shoes should comfortably support the insole. A velcro strap was used to fix the insole in place inside the shoes [22,30]. Sandals and moccasin styles of shoes should be forbidden because they don't allow the support that the patient needs [32-33].

Gait Analysis

- Before the testing procedure, the child was instructed with the test procedure. Three attempts were recorded using a mid-gait protocol. If any participant hesitated, the trial was redone. Both feet were used in data collection [16].
- Internal joint peak moments were recorded using the VICON 3D motion analysis system (Vicon Motion Systems Ltd., Oxford, UK). The system was used to record the pathway of reflective markers using eight computerized cameras. The data were sampled at a frequency of 100 Hz. Kinetic data were recorded by two force plates (Kistler Instrument AG, Switzerland) integrated with the motion analysis system to record the hip, knee and ankle moments with a sampling rate of 1000 Hz. All kinetics data were filtered using a fourth-order low-pass Butterworth filter with a 20 Hz cutoff frequency and was normalized to the child's body weight [10].
- 15 passively reflective markers (10 mm diameter) were applied on common and exact anatomic landmarks using double-sided adhesive tape; one upon the sacrum and bilaterally on the following: anterior superior iliac spine, middle thigh, lateral knee (directly lateral to axis of rotation), middle

tibia (the middle point between the knee marker and the lateral malleolus), lateral malleolus, and heel and forefoot between the second and third metatarsal heads [2,10].

- Before starting the gait analysis assessment, the child was asked to walk some trails along the walkway at a self- selected speed to be familiar with the experiment. Then, the child walks bare feet at a normal velocity over a 10-meter walkway during which the 3Dspatial position of each marker was recorded. The best data of three tests were used in the analysis. The test in which all the markers were obviously and accurately detected by the system was considered as the best data [2]. A 2-min rest was allowed between the three trails. A trial was confirmed when subjects walked with no visible change in gait mechanics, but it was excluded in case the foot was planted on the edge of the force plate.
- Re-evaluation for the kinetic variables was done in the same manner after accomplishing 6 and 12-months period of wearing the FI.

2.2 Statistical analysis

Data analysis was applied using the SPSS 22. The mean and standard deviation ($m \pm SD$) of foot, knee, and hip peak moments during the stance phase from sagittal, frontal and transverse planes were calculated for each child. Normal distribution of data was checked using the Shapiro-Wilk test for all variables. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) with repeated measures was used to compare the pre, post 6-months, and post 12-months treatment values. If significant, the post hoc test was used, with a significance level of $P < 0.05$.

3. RESULTS

The demographic data of 30 children with FFF were obtained and listed in Table 1.

Table 1. The demographic data (mean $\pm$ SD) of the children with FFF.

Age (years)	11.2 $\pm$ 2
Height (m)	1.56 $\pm$ 0.6
Weight (kg)	54.3 $\pm$ 7
Body mass index (kg/m ²)	20.1 $\pm$ 4.5
AI	0.28 $\pm$ 0.07

Throughout the 12 months period, the daily time of wearing their shoes with insoles was ranging from 6 to 9 hours, and the children or their parents did not report any adverse effects from wearing their shoes during this period.

As shown in table (2), after 6 months of wearing their shoes with FI, the children with FFF gained some little changes in their lower extremities' moments. There were only significant decreases in the peak moments of foot eversion (38.3%), forefoot, knee, and hip abductions (11.1%, 10.6%, and 9%) respectively, and hip flexion (27%).

The main new observed changes within the second 6 months of treatment were significant increases in the peak moments of ankle dorsiflexion (16.6%), forefoot adduction (40%). On the opposite side, the peak moments of foot inversion (21.4%), tibial internal rotation (33.3%) and hip extension (7%) were significantly decreased.

Comparing the pre-treatment mean values with the 12-months post-treatment mean values, the children additionally gained new significant decreases in the peak moments of knee flexion (20.8%), knee extension (12.5%), and hip internal rotation (11.6%) moments. At the same time, all previously mentioned variables, in first and second 6-months, continued to change the same way they decrease or increase.

However, it could be summarized that all the measured peak moments around the foot region are changed during the full treatment period. On the other hand, most of the peak moments around the knee and hip are decreased and others are not respondent to FI like hip and knee adduction and external rotation.

Moreover, from the above results, regarding the percentage of improvements in each joint in the lower extremity throughout the 12- months treatment period, it could be judged that both foot and knee are mostly and quickly showing their responses to FI in both frontal and transvers planes, while the hip joint is mostly and quickly respondent from both sagittal and frontal planes.

Table 2. Comparison of the mean values of the peak moments of ankle, knee and hip during gait stance before treatment, post 6 months, and post 12 months.

Moments (N.m/kg)	Pre TTT (m ± SD)	Post 6 months (m ± SD)	Post 12 months (m ± SD)	P value (Post 6 months Vs Pre TTT)	P value (Post 12 months Vs post 6 months) (% of change)	P value (Post 12 months Vs pre TTT) (% of change)
Ankle dorsiflexion	0.11±0.03	0.12±0.02	0.14±0.01	0.4	0.04 (16.6%)	0.002 (27.2%)
ankle plantar flexion	0.87±0.12	0.83±0.11	0.81±0.12	0.14	0.61	0.01 (6%)
foot eversion	0.13±0.05	0.08±0.04	0.04±0.03	0.001 (38.3%)	0.001 (50%)	0.001 (69.2%)
foot inversion	0.16±0.07	0.14±0.06	0.11±0.03	0.12	0.01 (21.4%)	0.001 (31.2%)
Forefoot abduction	0.18±0.03	0.16±0.02	0.15±0.03	0.001 (11.1%)	0.1	0.001 (16.6%)
Forefoot adduction	0.04±0.01	0.05±0.03	0.07±0.04	0.1	0.001 (40%)	0.001 (75%)
Knee flexion	0.24±0.08	0.22±0.09	0.19±0.05	0.3	0.07	0.001 (20.8%)
knee extension	0.48±0.17	0.45±0.13	0.41±0.11	0.4	0.2	0.01 (12.5%)
knee abduction	0.66±0.016	0.59±0.15	0.54±0.15	0.03 (10.6%)	0.1	0.001 (18.1%)
knee adduction	0.26±0.02	0.27±0.07	0.27±0.08	0.6	0.9	0.6
Tibia internal rotation	0.06±0.03	0.06±0.01	0.04±0.01	0.9	0.001 (33.3%)	0.001 (33.3%)
Tibia external rotation	0.2±0.09	0.18±0.06	0.18±0.03	0.2	0.9	0.2
Hip flexion	1.01±0.16	0.73±0.15	0.7±0.16	0.001 (27%)	0.54	0.001 (70%)
Hip extension	0.68±0.18	0.66±0.08	0.61±0.1	0.07	0.001 (7%)	0.001 (10.6%)
Hip abduction	0.44±0.02	0.4±0.03	0.36±0.01	0.001 (9%)	0.001 (10%)	0.001 (18%)
Hip adduction	0.25±0.11	0.22±0.08	0.22±0.02	0.09	0.9	0.09
Hip internal rotation	0.43±0.09	0.4±0.11	0.38±0.08	0.1	0.4	0.01 (11.6%)
Hip external rotation	0.33±0.09	0.33±0.07	0.32±0.04	0.9	0.7	0.7

m: mean; SD: standard deviation; significant difference: P < 0.05

4. Discussion

Based on the review of previous literature, no research works studied the long- term effect of foot orthosis on flat feet, specifically in children. Most of the works studied its immediate effect in adults or even in children, except one study for Jafarnejhadgero et al. [34], who studied its effect on gait kinetics and kinematics in young boys aged 8-14 years and for only 4 months of intervention? Because of this scanty data and evidence, our study is considered to be the first one to examine the long-term effect (12 months) of FI on foot kinetics in children with FFF.

Our data analysis revealed that, after the first 6 months of treatment, the use of FI could reduce some of the lower extremity peak moments, which are ankle eversion, forefoot, knee and hip abductions and hip flexor moment. These come in agreement with Jafarnejhadgero et al. [34] who concluded that FO could decrease the ankle eversion, hip and knee abduction peak moments in the dominant lower limb when fourteen boys of

younger age with FFF wore FO for four successive months. Leung *et al.* [5] also previously reported a significant reduction in the foot pronation angle, velocity and time to maximal pronation by using an orthosis. Mundermann *et al.* [35] was partly different when recorded a significant and positive relationship between the foot eversion and knee adduction, instead of our gained knee abduction, peak moments during running with shod orthoses.

When the treatment period was extended up to 12 months, the previous moments become more reduced, in addition to other new responses of peak moments. Peak moments of ankle dorsiflexion and forefoot adduction were significantly increased, while plantar flexion, forefoot abduction, knee flexion, extension, tibial internal rotation, hip extension and internal rotation become clearly decreased during the second 6 months of treatment. Hsu *et al.* [36], with their study on forefoot varus abnormality, agreed only with our results in that FO reduced the ankle inversion moment, but they disagreed in that FO increased, rather than decreased, the knee internal and abduction moments in the late stance. Another difference was that decreased hip adduction and external rotation moments, as our results did not show any change in the adduction or external rotation moments around the hip.

From the above results, the foot was the most apparent respondent, in its all measured variables, to the application of FI rather than the knee or the hip joints. In addition, it was observed that the greatest percentages of change in the measured moments of foot or knee, occurred in the frontal and transverse planes, in spite of un neglectable changes occurred in the foot, knee and hip within the sagittal plane. This comes in harmony with the concept of the coupling relationship between foot inversion/eversion and the tibial rotation. The results in this context also match Engg and pierrynowski [37] and Nawoczinski *et al.* [38]. They recorded a significant decrease in foot kinetics from frontal and transverse planes during the heel strike and mid-stance phases of the gait cycle. Sinclair *et al.* [39] had also demonstrated that lower limb kinetics were improved in runners when they used medial orthoses from both coronal and transverse planes. In agreement with our results, Razeghi and Batt [28], declared a significant reduction in some variables of lower limb kinematics during stance phase in either in walking or in running such as foot pronation, calcaneal eversion and rear foot movements in response to foot orthosis.

On the opposite side, our results do not meet the conclusion of Kulcu *et al.*[2] whom results revealed that FI has no significant effect in normalizing the forces acting on the foot or the whole lower extremity in adults with FFF, but this may be attributed to studying only the immediate effect and not the long-lasting effect of insoles. Also, their study was applied to adults and not on children.

The gained results seem to be due to the prolonged effect of FI on correcting the foot structure alignment in terms of foot pronation, forefoot abduction and tibial internal rotation. It also provided more stability, reducing tension on the soft tissue structures during loading [40]. This concept was admitted by Kuhn *et al.*, [41] who radiologically investigated the effect of FO in subjects with FFF. They found significant improvements in foot angles and its alignment during weight bearing. Saeedi *et al.* [42] found that, despite a single case, modified UCBL orthosis could correct the alignment of ankle, subtalar and knee joints by decreasing the degree of pronation and knee internal rotation. The orthoses can also provide more comfort by decreasing the stress over the plantar ligaments in the flat foot.

The insoles are thought to effectively increase the height of foot arch, shift the weight-bearing points from the midfoot to the forefoot and to the heel, suppress the foot eversion angle, and reduces the rearfoot angular velocity [43]. However, this contradicts the conclusions by Mosca [44], and Mortazafi *et al.* [45] who told

that asymptomatic FFF children did not require any foot orthosis to correct the flat feet, but their decisions were based on studying only the immediate effects of foot orthosis.

Further, the results could also be viewed that the ground reaction force (GRF) may be decreased with the presence of FI. It has been concluded that GRF may decrease up to 11 % during the mid-stance, which could provide again more comfort during standing or walking [42].

The post-treatment findings are expected also to be due to the changes in the electrical muscle activity as explained by Nawoczenski and Ludewig [46], and by George and Adam [47] who reported that tibialis anterior and peroneus longus muscles have increased their electrical activities in shoes combined with orthosis rather than in shoes worn alone. The tibialis anterior muscle, which is one of the important ankle stabilizers, is inserted medially to the subtalar joint, so the increase of its contraction will contribute to the decrease in foot pronation after the heel strike and during the stance phase. The peroneus longus muscle, representing ankle lateral stability, has an insertion at the base of the big toe, and so, its contraction during the mid-stance phase will assist the first ray plantarflexion. The subsequent big toe dorsiflexion moment will assist the windlass mechanism and the foot sagittal plane moments during walking.

These obtained results of the current study could be also explained according to Nigg et al. [48] and Kakihana et al. [49] as that the center of the pressure is shifted to the direction of insole insertion. Hence, the lever arm of the ground reaction force to the center of each joint in the lower limb and the produced moments will be affected. The FI was thought to increase the total contact area under the sole of the foot. Hence, redistribution of the forces can decrease the plantar pressure below the first metatarsal head and the medial side of the heel [28].

Finally, the FI are proposed to affect the biofeedback mechanism. The FI that are placed on the medial side of the foot will stimulate the exteroceptive signaling. Hence the efferent to foot investors will be increased, leading to a reduction in the foot evertor activity with subsequent effective performance and comfortability [38]. In line with this, the concept of central adaptation appears to play a role in improving the muscle performance when using FI for 12 months [50].

Study limitations:

Our study may indeed have some limitations. Given that the activity of the lower limb muscles proprioceptors may have had a role in the long term gained results in response to FI [51]. Our adopted methods did not investigate the electrical muscle activity e.g. electromyography or nerve conduction studies or the possible radiological changes in foot structure. Another limitation is that the assessment was made for children during only walking condition, not in running or in jumping conditions to confirm the obtained corrections. Lastly, the study was applied to female children rather than on both males and females, taking into consideration the developmental, and biomechanical differences between both sexes at the same age level.

5. Conclusion

This study implied the effect of FI on lower limb kinetics. Our results proved that FI could produce changes in all of the peak moments acting around the foot region, most of the moments acting around the knee and hip joints when they are applied for a prolonged period, successive 12 months, of time. Hence, we could consider that FI is a feasible effective intervention to correct the medial longitudinal arch and improve the disturbed lower limb kinetics in girls with FFF. Future studies are recommended to measure the long-term effect of FI on kinematic parameters in the lower extremities as well as the reflection of both kinetic and kinematic

changes on the quality of life in children or in adults with FFF.

6. Conflict of interest

None of the authors in this study have a related conflict of interest.

7. Acknowledgement

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